

WISE AI Testbed Evaluation Framework - Full consolidated version

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About this document

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Table of Contents

0. Context & Strategic Fit (Non-Scored)	3
0.1 Tool Purpose.....	4
0.2 Development Stage.....	4
1. Domain: Evidence of Effectiveness & Support	4
1.1 Existing Evidence & Impact.....	4
1.2 Provider Support & Capacity.....	5
2. Domain: Usability, Infrastructure & Training	6
2.1 Technical Interoperability & Infrastructure.....	6
2.2 User Experience (UX).....	6
2.3 Training & Professional Development (Quality + Cost).....	7
3. Domain: Pedagogical Effectiveness & Workflow	8
3.1 Alignment & Transformation.....	8
3.2 Personalization & Differentiation Workflow.....	9
3.3 Home–School Use to Support Personalisation.....	10
3.4 Agency & Feedback.....	10
4. Domain: Equity and Accessibility	12
4.1 Actionable Analytics.....	12
4.2 Cultural & Linguistic Responsiveness.....	13
4.3 Accessibility.....	13
5. Domain: Ethics, Data Privacy and Security	13
5.1 Bias Mitigation & Ethical Design.....	13
5.2 Transparency & Compliance.....	14
5.3 Data Privacy & Sovereignty.....	15
6. Domain: Cost & Sustainability	15
6.1 Total Cost of Ownership (TCO).....	15

0. Context & Strategic Fit (Non-Scored)

Provides necessary context before scoring begins.

0.1 Tool Purpose

- **Question:** What is the primary educational purpose or function(s) of the selected AI product?
- **Categories:**
 - Personalised learning
 - Assessment
 - Classroom management
 - Lesson planning
 - Homework assignment

0.2 Development Stage

- **Question:** What stage of development is the AI tool in?
- **Categories:**
 - Prototype
 - Developing product
 - Piloting
 - Deployment
 - Scaling

1. Domain: Evidence of Effectiveness & Support

Focus: Does the tool have a track record, and will the provider support us?

1.1 Existing Evidence & Impact

- **Question:** What is the extent of existing evidence of the AI tool's implementation in school settings?
 - **Metric (Existence of evidence):**

- 1 = No evidence exists or is inaccessible.
- 2 = Evidence from 1-2 sources.
- 3 = Evidence from multiple sources.
- **Metric (Evidence sources):**
 - 1 = Internal/supplier evaluations only.
 - 2 = Supplier and user evaluations.
 - 3 = External evaluations (non-profits/marketplaces).
 - 4 = External evaluations (research institutions/academia).
- **Open ended question:** *Please attach available evidence sources or add online links.*
- **Question:** To what extent is there evidence that the AI tool supports improved outcomes for diverse learner groups?
 - **Metric (Impact on Diverse Learners):**
 - 1 = No disaggregated evidence.
 - 2 = Limited disaggregation (not linked to differentiation).
 - 3 = Strong disaggregation (shows impact for specific groups).
 - **Metric (Tool tested with diverse populations):**
 - 1 = No evidence of testing.
 - 2 = Tested with limited groups.
 - 3 = Some evidence of diversity.
 - 4 = Tested with broad and diverse range of backgrounds.

1.2 Provider Support & Capacity

- **Question:** To what extent is the provider able to provide initial and ongoing support?
 - **Metric (Free trial availability):**
 - 1 = No.
 - 2 = Yes.
 - **Metric (Local support channels):**

- 1 = No available local support.
 - 2 = Limited available local support.
 - 3 = Ongoing available local support.
 - **Metric (Provider responsiveness):**
 - 1 = Adhoc level with no mechanisms.
 - 2 = Medium level with mechanisms that can be improved.
 - 3 = Strong level with mechanisms for feedback and support.
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2. Domain: Usability, Infrastructure & Training

Focus: Can we technically run it, and can teachers learn it?

2.1 Technical Interoperability & Infrastructure

- **Question:** Can the tool be easily integrated with existing digital systems (LMS, SSO) and does it require new hardware?
 - **Metric (Integration):**
 - 1 = Requires demanding set-up or additional purchases.
 - 2 = Requires some manageable set-up.
 - 3 = Can seamlessly integrate with existing systems.
 - **Metric (Device compatibility):**
 - 1 = Requires new/high-end devices.
 - 2 = May run on some devices but requires upgrades.
 - 3 = Works on most existing devices.
 - 4 = Fully compatible with existing hardware.
 - **Metric (Offline capabilities):**
 - 1 = Cannot function offline.
 - 2 = Limited offline functionality, key features unavailable.
 - 3 = Limited offline functionality, key features available.

- 4 = Fully functional offline.

2.2 User Experience (UX)

- **Question:** Is the tool intuitive, and are the aesthetics appropriate?
 - **Metric (Intuition):**
 - 1 = Low (Hard to use/navigate).
 - 2 = Medium.
 - 3 = High (Easy to use/navigate and self-learn).
 - **Metric (Aesthetics & Functionality):** *(Based on age-appropriate visuals, lack of clutter, sound controls, clarity of workflows, sensitivity to touch, speed of response, easily retrievable instructions)*
 - 1 = Scores < 50% of mentioned aspects.
 - 2 = Scores 50%.
 - 3 = Scores > 50%.

2.3 Training & Professional Development (Quality + Cost)

- **Question:** Is there sufficient technical guidance, what is the format, ease of use, and is it affordable?
 - **Metric (Training Availability):**
 - 1 = No available training materials.
 - 2 = Available for some tool features.
 - 3 = Available for all tool features.
 - **Metric (Training Materials Ease of Use):**
 - 1 = Difficult to access or non-engaging.
 - 2 = Medium level engaging.
 - 3 = Highly engaging and easy to use.
 - **Metric (Training Time):**
 - 1 = Little to no indication of time needed.
 - 2 = Time indication provided but not feasible.

- 3 = Time indication provided and feasible.
 - **Metric (PD Format):**
 - 1 = No available support.
 - 2 = PD available on demand.
 - 3 = PD offered with license.
 - 4 = Community of practice exists globally or regionally.
 - **Metric (Teacher Training Cost):**
 - 1 = No training or high additional cost.
 - 2 = Optional training at extra cost.
 - 3 = Training included in pricing.
 - 4 = High-quality training, openly accessible/scalable.
 - **Open ended question:** *Please attach or share links to any available training materials or teacher usage certifications.*
-

3. Domain: Pedagogical Effectiveness & Workflow

Focus: Does it improve teaching/learning, and is the workflow manageable?

3.1 Alignment & Transformation

- **Question:** Does the tool align with our mission, curriculum, and transform learning tasks?
 - **Metric (Alignment with educational philosophy):**
 - 1 = Little alignment.
 - 2 = Moderate alignment.
 - 3 = Strong alignment.
 - **Metric (Curricular alignment per subject):**
 - 1 = Little to no alignment (0-29%).

- 2 = Some alignment (30-50%).
- 3 = Most alignment (51-80%).
- 4 = Near complete alignment (81-100%).
- **Metric (Matching learning goals):**
 - 1 = Non-existing.
 - 2 = Secondary goals (Facilitative).
 - 3 = Primary goals (Instructional).
- **Metric (Task Transformation - SAMR):**
 - 1 = Substitution.
 - 2 = Augmentation.
 - 3 = Modification.
 - 4 = Redefinition.
- **Metric (Dedicated educational team):**
 - 1 = Non-existing.
 - 2 = Developed with an education team.
 - 3 = Developed with an experienced education team aligning responses with sound theory.

3.2 Personalization & Differentiation Workflow

- **Question:** Does the tool offer personalized pathways, diverse scaffolds, and is it easy to set up fairly?
 - **Metric (Personalised pathways):**
 - 1 = No capability.
 - 2 = Limited/pre-scripted scenarios.
 - 3 = Comprehensive/adaptive towards mastery.
 - 4 = Comprehensive/adaptive + teacher-orchestrated.
 - **Metric (Differentiated content, scaffolds, and modalities):** *(Multiple reading levels, built-in scaffolds, multiple modalities like audio/visual/text etc)*
 - 1 = Minimal (Cosmetic variation).

- 2 = Moderate (Offers 50% or less).
- 3 = Strong (Offers > 50%).
- **Metric (Learner model and diagnosis):**
 - 1 = Limited (Single data point).
 - 2 = Basic (Several data points, infrequent updates).
 - 3 = Strong (Multiple data sources, ongoing profile).
 - 4 = Advanced (Rich learner profile easily understood by all).
- **Metric (Ease of use for differentiation):**
 - 1 = Cumbersome.
 - 2 = Usable with effort.
 - 3 = Streamlined.
 - 4 = Designed to reduce workload.
- **Metric (Fairness of Personalisation):**
 - 1 = High risk (Locks into "low" tracks).
 - 2 = Some safeguards.
 - 3 = Fairness-aware design.
 - 4 = Fairness by design + transparency.

3.3 Home–School Use to Support Personalisation

- **Question:** Can the tool be meaningfully used in both school and home settings to support continuous personalised learning?
 - **Answers (Rubric):**
 - 1 = No home–school connection.
 - 2 = Medium (Learners can log in, but data isn't integrated into planning).
 - 3 = Strong (Home/school data is integrated into analytics and teacher planning).

3.4 Agency & Feedback

- **Question:** Does the tool empower teachers/students, enhance relationships, and provide quality feedback?
 - **Metric (Teacher Empowerment):**
 - 1 = Undermines teacher role.
 - 2 = Limits teacher agency.
 - 3 = Actively supports teacher decision-making.
 - 4 = Amplifies and enhances teacher agency.
 - **Metric (Learner Autonomy):**
 - 1 = Over-relies on system automation.
 - 2 = Limited student initiative.
 - 3 = Encourages independent learning.
 - 4 = Strong support for learner voice/choice.
 - **Metric (Feedback Quality):**
 - 1 = Several quality issues.
 - 2 = Satisfactory.
 - 3 = Highly responsive, accessible, pedagogically sound.
 - **Metric (Impact on existing school processes):**
 - 1 = Disruptive.
 - 2 = Supports existing processes.
 - 3 = Integrates and enhances with moderate adjustment.
 - 4 = Seamlessly aligns/enhances.
 - **Metric (Effect on teaching and learner relationships):**
 - 1 = Undermines/creates distance.
 - 2 = No discernible impact.
 - 3 = Supports relationships.
 - 4 = Actively enhances relational pedagogies.

- **Metric (Effect on accountability mechanisms of students):**
 - 1 = Reduces transparency.
 - 2 = Changes unclear.
 - 3 = Maintains clear accountability.
 - 4 = Strengthens accountability.
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4. Domain: Equity and Accessibility

Focus: Can we see what is happening, and is it inclusive for all learners?

4.1 Actionable Analytics

- **Question:** Are dashboards available, transparent, and equity-aware?
 - **Metric (Data collection ability):**
 - 1 = Non-existing.
 - 2 = Medium (Generic usage data).
 - 3 = High (Specific learning events, disaggregated).
 - **Metric (Transparency/Explainability):**
 - 1 = Opaque.
 - 2 = Partially transparent.
 - 3 = Transparent with control.
 - 4 = Transparent + co-designed.
 - **Metric (Equity-aware analytics):**
 - 1 = No (Whole-class averages only).
 - 2 = Limited (Manual filtering only).
 - 3 = Strong (Easy filtering by group/needs).
 - 4 = Strong + guided actions.
 - **Metric (Suggestions to teachers & Override capability):**
 - 1 = No suggestions/no space for collaboration.

- 2 = Suggestions need enhancement; inputs optional.
- 3 = Suggestions available; teacher inputs integrated into system.
- **Metric (Suggestions to parents):**
 - 1 = No suggestions.
 - 2 = Suggestions available but need enhancement.
 - 3 = Suggestions available with teacher engagement opportunity.

4.2 Cultural & Linguistic Responsiveness

- **Question:** Does it support our language and culture?
 - **Metric (Arabic Support):**
 - 1 = No Arabic support.
 - 2 = Limited/Basic.
 - 3 = Functional.
 - 4 = Strong/Arabic-first (Gulf variants).
 - **Metric (Cultural Adaptability):**
 - 1 = Not responsive.
 - 2 = Relies on user input.
 - 3 = Can be adapted without user input.
 - 4 = Homegrown for the context.

4.3 Accessibility

- **Question:** Is it compliant with digital accessibility standards?
 - **Metric (Digital accessibility):**
 - 1 = Inaccessible to learners with disabilities.
 - 2 = Somewhat accessible.
 - 3 = Comprehensively accessible.
 - **Open Ended:** *Please elaborate on accessibility features.*
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5. Domain: Ethics, Data Privacy and Security

Focus: Is it safe, fair, and compliant?

5.1 Bias Mitigation & Ethical Design

- **Question:** Were stakeholders consulted, and does the tool mitigate bias?
 - **Metric (Stakeholder consultation):**
 - 1 = No involvement.
 - 2 = Limited consultation with educators.
 - 3 = Co-designed with teachers/students.
 - **Metric (Developer ethics training):**
 - 1 = No developer AI ethics training.
 - 2 = Basic or informal awareness.
 - 3 = Some developers have formal training.
 - 4 = Majority trained in ethics, education, and child rights.
 - **Metric (Bias mitigation):**
 - 1 = No mitigation.
 - 2 = Acknowledged but unclear.
 - 4 = Consistently tested and mitigated for race/gender/culture.
 - **Open Ended:** *Please attach your policies for equity and bias mitigation (or any equivalent in your company).*

5.2 Transparency & Compliance

- **Question:** Is data collection transparent, legitimate, and justified, and does it comply with national/organizational laws?
 - *Evaluator Note: The evaluator should compare company documents against institutional policies here.*
 - **Metric (Supplier transparency on data storage and usage):**
 - 1 = No information available.
 - 2 = Technical/vague descriptions.

- 3 = Clear communication available.
- 4 = Publicly available, accessible explanations.
- **Metric (Legitimacy of data use and rationale):**
 - 1 = Unclear or unjustified use.
 - 2 = Use is somewhat relevant.
 - 3 = Clearly tied to improving education outcomes.
 - 4 = Transparent, minimal, and justified.
- **Metric (Legal and policy alignment with institution):**
 - 1 = Does not comply / cannot determine.
 - 2 = Partially compliant.
 - 3 = Complies with Qatari and school policies.
 - 4 = Complies with policies and data use is fully auditable.

5.3 Data Privacy & Sovereignty

- **Question:** Is data stored locally and legally with designated safe zones?
 - **Metric (Data hosting location):**
 - 1 = Entirely outside location
 - 2 = Optional location hosting, not guaranteed.
 - 3 = Have the capability to host locally.
 - 4 = Homegrown/Hosted in location by default.
 - **Metric (Safe zones):**
 - 1 = Continuous monitoring.
 - 2 = Clear user control in some areas.
 - 3 = Clearly designated assessment-free spaces.
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6. Domain: Cost & Sustainability

Focus: Is it financially viable?

6.1 Total Cost of Ownership (TCO)

- **Question:** What is the full financial picture?
 - **Metric (Overall affordability):**
 - 1 = High cost, unclear benefits.
 - 2 = Costs known, hard to assess benefits.
 - 3 = Costs known, moderate benefits.
 - 4 = Costs transparent, justified, clear benefits.
 - **Metric (Licensing clarity):**
 - 1 = Complex, frequent renewals.
 - 2 = Moderate burden.
 - 3 = Reasonable, predictable.
 - 4 = Flexible, school-friendly.
 - **Metric (Maintenance):**
 - 1 = Costly or school responsible.
 - 2 = Available at additional charge.
 - 3 = Basic included.
 - 4 = Proactive support included.